

FROM BALANCE TO BRILLIANCE: NEXUS OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE, SELF-EFFICACY, COMMITMENT AND CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

This study is conducted to examine the impact of work-life balance on organizational citizenship behaviour, where self-efficacy and organizational commitment are utilized as intervening variables. This is quantitative research. Data is collected from the healthcare sector, with a sample of 360 respondents. SPSS is used for statistical analysis. Statistical analysis has shown the strong impact of work-life balance on organizational citizenship behaviour, and proves the intervening effect of self-efficacy and organizational commitment. The policies and practices that bring balance in life, are seen to significantly enhance the OCB levels to such extent that employees prefer to add extra value to their roles. Moreover, Social Exchange Theory explains the link between work-life balance and organizational citizenship behaviour. The study has proved the importance of work-life harmony, it's worth and impact on workforce. In this fast-paced era, retention is a big challenge for organizations, by implementing employee-centric practices, businesses can combat with this challenge, easily. People want comfort and balance and if the corporate sector prioritize this, it will solve retention issue and also foster organizational citizenship behaviour. This study has thoroughly investigated the role of self-efficacy and commitment in the pursuit of OCB.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary social sciences, the term WLB has remained the centre of attention for practitioners and researchers. The evolution and advancement of WLB shows the major change in social attitude, behaviour, and expectations towards work (Wong., 2021). Organizations are compelled to reconsider the traditional work set-up because employees now expect to pay attention to their family life, like they prioritize their work (Davidescu.,2020). The changing nature of WLB is linked with technological advancement and globalization which has, reshaped the work environments and organisational dynamics (Gagnano., 2020). With the advanced digital tools and AI, now employees must have more autonomy

over their work, schedule, and tasks (Ferrara., 2022). WLB is deeply associated with job satisfaction and well-being and both are inevitable for organizational success (Bocean., 2023). Research shows that the level of organizational commitment increases with strong application of WLB practices (Weng., 2023). Individuals are focusing on balancing work and personal life, and now employees expect their organisations to provide certain WLB facilities. Scholarly research has increased focus on finding and exploring innovative ways and strategies to enhance WLB outcomes in organisations. From meaningful interventions to flexible work approaches are being explored, to promote employee well-being,

satisfaction and productivity (Marais., 2022). The scholarly attention towards WLB has broadened the priorities of organisations towards employee well-being and organisational effectiveness (E-Vahadati., 2022). Researchers have identified WLB as a multidimensional construct that covers many domains like self-efficacy, psychological well-being and social support (Arslan G, 2021). Furthermore, the increase in knowledge, economic changes, and globalization of businesses have increased the demand of WLB as a strategic imperative for organisational success. Research explains a good relationship of WLB and employee happiness. Employees who see their firm as an upholder and promoter of WLB, show the immense level of job fulfilment, engagement, commitment and decreased amount of anxiety and pressure among employees (Jayaraman., 2023). WLB increases the quality of life, job satisfaction and engagement. Employees become dissatisfied and organizations face retention problems if WLB policies are not implemented (Ferreira and Gomes., 2023). Which, in turn, leads to enhanced turnover, absenteeism, low productivity and decreased organizational success. WLB plays a very basic and vital role in improving the efficiency and effectiveness of an organisation. As it helps to enhance the psychological, sentimental and cognitive stability of employees. According to Shaffer (2016), and Henry & Beauregard (2008), a lower level of WLB badly affects the cognitive ability of employees which also affects organisational productivity. People work because of necessity as they have no choice to choose from their desired jobs, so, they are seen as less passionate and not committed. Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) has its unique significance as it strengthens retention rate, employee's love for the organization, and organizational productivity. Cieri, Holmes, Pettit & Abbott (2005) says (in their research), now organizations need to form WLB policies much strong to achieve organisational performance to meet the competitive environment of the market. There is a lack of a notable theoretical model for linking WLB to OCB. Thus, the study examines whether WLB influences OCB, while, organizational commitment and self-efficacy are examined as mediating variables. There's a major gap in research related to the mental and intellectual conditions of

employees. OCB refers to an effective, discretionary and spontaneous behaviour that's not directly appraised. OCB is a voluntary behaviour that employees express towards their work, tasks, events, challenges or organisation. It's like aligning with organizational rules, and culture, doing extra tasks and obeying the policies. WLB has a great effect on it. Poulouse & N. (2018) identified that there exist some factors that dominate the WLB including, individual emotional intelligence, and psychological wellbeing. So, WLB can be defined as the capability of an individual to maintain and manage all components of life. According to Mahsunah & Musbikhin (2023), there are other factors that dominate self-efficacy including, gender, culture, nature of the task, role at work, and perspective about personal abilities

According to Rinni Indriyani (2019), WLB has a strong connection with OC. It has a very positive impact on employees as well. OC is considered a psychological connection between employees and organisations (Meyer, 2012). With the passage of time, the OC has evolved and changed. Recent study has found a decline in affective commitment, and the enhancement of A.C. is a long-term process (Solinger, 2015). Other research has proved that OC is a predictor of employee retention (Basel Al-Jabari and Issam Ghazzawi, 2019) and has become the centre of attention of the HR Dept for decades (Idris, 2014). The OC in an organization is important as it impact on loyalty and retention degrees (Meyer 1996).

With the passage of time, the working patterns have changed and so the organisation consider it important to bring innovation and creativity to the organization, for this, proper strategic ways are important, and proper planning and strategy have significant importance to gain any goal or to achieve any target whether it's relevant to business, optimistic environment or to bring change to the organisation (Martinus Nahak and Lena Elliton, 2022).

2.0 Literature Review:

2.1 Work-life balance:

Work-life balance is simply the capacity of a person to maintain balance in life, and how he/she maintains a balance between work and family life. In the advanced era, we're witnessing many

technological, social, and demographic changes that have impacted the work environments and originated a diverse workforce with diverse backgrounds, expectations, and needs from organizations. The rise in dual-career families and rapidly dissolving psychological contracts between employees and employers has raised major concerns across the business sector. In this regard, the policies with the change in WLB can generate a significant effect for employees and the organization as well, which may include retention of potential employees, decreased ratio of absenteeism, improved employee performance level, and better recruitment. Many researches have been made to stress the importance of WLB as it helps to increase job satisfaction and career development among employees. Employers must organize a feedback system to continuously check the effectiveness and impact of the WLB programs and practices in the organization (Bello, Tula, Omotoye, Kess-Momoh, Daraojimba, 2024). Now employees want a relaxed life with no pressure of work, this urge has become so strong that the imbalance creates conflicts and stress among employees (Robbins & Judge, 2017). As known, organizations need hardworking employees with full potential to achieve the set goals and targets organisations need employees that work hard to achieve the company targets and on the other hand, employees have their own lives and family needs for which they work hard. As organizations require full potential and contributions, however, workers focus on maintaining stability in all areas of life. In this context, WLB is very important. WLB plays a very pivotal role for dual-career families as well (Pradhan, Kumari, and Jena 2016). Empirical data shows that the idea of stability in life among employees relates to no workload, a stress-free environment, and easy work (Allen 2010). Similarly, there is another aspect, the capability to utilize time wisely, which refers to the balance between the years given to a career and also time given to the family, for instance, an individual needs time for family and for managing other aspects of life. According to Suryalena and Murtafia 2015, A good work environment and conditions are necessary to make the employees feel relaxed, satisfied, and professionally motivated.

WLB has three main and basic components balanced time, balanced work, and family involvement (Wong,

Bandar Saili 2017). At this time, organizations should focus on flexible schedules, a relaxed environment, and balanced WLB rather than work politics or bureaucracy because employees need WLB (Aydin 2016). The best type of WLB policies can be made with the conversation and discussion between employer and employees (Oa 2018). There are some WLB strategies that can be adopted by companies.

- a) Flexible schedule
- b) Remote working, where employees can work with ease at home without the pressure and wasting their energy.
- c) To permit an easy work schedule to workers who pursue studies.

The yearly leave chart must be made in the start of every year to prevent any interference in whole schedule (Meenakshi 2013, Oa 2019, Lazer 2010).

2.2 Organization Citizenship Behaviour:

Organ (1988), explained that organizational citizenship behaviour is a behaviour that employees show like support, care, and helping colleagues apart from the official job expectations. It is the attitude that has no prize but it strongly promotes and strengthens the performance of the organization. Organ 1988, used the term discretionary which means the behaviour which is not included in a formal job description. It shows that high levels of organizational citizenship behaviour are individual's choice but low levels of organizational citizenship behaviour do not lead to punishment. Robbins (2003), explained that OCB refers to external discretionary attitude which is not mentioned in description of employment, it does promote the effectiveness of the organization. OCB was first elaborated by Dennis Organ in 1988, which was referred to as "extra-role behaviour" among employees, as explained by Katz (1964). According to Dennis Organ, OCB as a behaviour that is optional or non-compulsory, which isn't directly shaped by a formal reward system but it improves the functioning of an organization. Organ further explained OCB as non-compulsory behaviour related to work that contributes to the betterment and improvement of psychological and social contexts that support task performance (Lai, 2016; Organ, 1997). Different names have been used for OCB such as Perceived organizational membership (Masterson and Stamper,

2003) and compulsory citizenship behaviour (Vigodo, Gadot 2006). Furthermore, many concepts have been explained and introduced by different researchers, all referred to the concept of OCB by Organ (1988).

According to Organ (1988), organisation citizenship behaviour dimensions are as follows:

- Altruism: This dimension is related to the aid giver.
- Conscientiousness: This dimension refers to innovative actions to improve organisational productivity, helping co-workers, working as volunteers and motivating others.
- Sportsmanship: a dimension that accepts the situation less than the ideal circumstances without objections.
- Courtesy: this dimension refers to good relationships with co-workers to avoid problems.
- Civic Virtue: this dimension includes the effort of employees to achieve the set goals and to bring innovation to the traditional working of organisation.

According to Organ (2006), two factors influence the OCB:

1. Internal Factors: the factors derived from employees such as job satisfaction, organisational conflict, employee morale and motivation.
2. External Factors: the factors come from employers such as leadership style, work environment organisational culture etc.

The OCB is a clear concept, which means that it is an extra effort from an employee to work beyond limits, to bring success in the organization. (Van Dyan 1994). These dimensions are very important and famous for describing OCB. Studies have shown that the impact of WLB inspires and motivates employees to move towards discretionary behaviour. It shows the direct effect of maintaining a balance of OCB and WLB among employees (Paradhan., 2016). Employer branding is important, it brings a sense of good corporate citizen among employees which uplevels OCB (Manuel Alfonso Garzón Castrillón, 2024). Chiaburu and Harrison (2008), explained if an employee expresses good behaviour, then it affects positively the co-worker to get engaged

in organizational citizenship behaviour. Bragger (2005), explained that role conflict negatively affects the level of OCB, suggesting that more role conflict leads an employee away from OCB. Consequently, new firms offer work-life balance facilities as part of this social exchange interaction with employees in HR policies.

According to Podaskoff (2000), OCB has many advantages, such as

- It enhances and boosts the employee's productivity
- It enhances the manager's performance
- It conserves the organisation's resources as a whole
- OCB saves scarce resource energy to maintain group functioning
- OCB plays a notable impact in the coordination of work activities
- It boosts good coordination among members of groups
- OCB improve the retention of best employees
- It enhances the stability of organisational performance
- OCB enhanced the capability of an organisation to bring creativity and innovation to its surroundings in accordance with market needs.

2.3 Self-Efficacy:

Self-efficacy is the capability of a person to respond or take action (in its best way) to counter a specific situation. According to Albert Bandura (1986), it is the self-analysis or self-awareness of a person of its own abilities and confidence level to complete a designated task. The main point is the perception of one's own capabilities to do something and not the perception of someone else (Mills, Pajares, Herron 2007.). Bandura (1978), has explained how self-efficacy dominates our beliefs, our actions, and persistence particularly when facing any challenge. According to Bandura (1978 and 1997), there are 4 origins of self-efficacy:

1. Mastery Experiences
2. Vicarious Experiences
3. Verbal Persuasion
4. Psychological or Effective states

Mastery experiences include the past experiences of achievements of similar actions or tasks. Vicarious Experiences come from the achievements of subordinates. Persuasive communication means the experience or opinion given from people. Effective states are related to a person's own thoughts and interpretations. This shows that how the self-awareness in terms of self-efficacy is built. Studies have shown its effect on education, achievement, success and learning capability. (Schunk Pajares 2002 1995). The useful/beneficial use of self-efficacy is when someone overestimates his/her capabilities in doing any task, it increases their efforts during tough situations (Artino., 2012). Significant levels of self-efficacy increase self-worth, which makes a person able to stay strong in any situation and to stay motivated to complete tasks. Less self-efficacy have negative effects which generate avoiding behaviours and negative thoughts that affect not only the performance but also the well-being of the person (Julie Waddington, 2023). If we talk about education sector, especially foreign languages, we find basics of self-efficacy: one employee focuses on learners, and others on teachers. The studies with emphasis on learners, self-efficacy helped to understand the association of learner's SE and motivation to learn a foreign language. It showed that self-efficacy is the first step towards a positive attitude to learning a new language (Waddington., 2019) & also helped the learners to strengthen their self-efficacy and self-regulatory strategies (Zhang., 2020). Different sources of self-efficacy explained by Bandura (1978), can be utilized to identify specific areas in which teachers can enhance learners' self-understanding and self-regulatory. For example, skill mastery, identifying to know the way with which the individuals perceive and remember their past achievements and how they take their shortcomings, failures, and successes. (Dornyei., 2001). Interpretations of past good and bad experiences can originate negative self-reflection (I could not do that because I am not capable of learning a new language) or find the point of improvement and constructively work on it to improve performance (I'll work on my shortcomings and try to focus on.....). Vicarious experience is related to performance experience that helps to build self-efficacy by seeing others' performance and certain actions (Waddington, 2019). These efforts are good

to lessen the anxieties and barriers that have been there, acting as hurdles in learning a new language for students (Horwitz, Horwitz & Cope., 1986). According to Mohammed (2023), self-efficacy is the confidence to accomplish any task and it's an important part of personal growth. It's the individual's ability to manage the situation according to their level of confidence and belief.

2.4 Organizational Commitment:

In this fast and advanced era, motivated, committed employees are important for corporate success and are very beneficial for a positive impact on business (Vieira, 2023). There's not a widely prescribed definition of organizational commitment, different scholars and professors have defined OC in different ways. According to Miller (2003), OC is the level to which an employee recognizes the organizational goals and wishes to remain part of the company. Avolio (2004), defined OC as an attitude where employees want to remain in a particular organization. Miller and Lee (2001) explained that OC is the level to which employees take part in the progress of an organization through their values and behaviours. The study of Allen and Meyer (1990) revealed that OC includes normative, affective and continuous commitment. Singh and Gupta (2015) said that it's a psychological state that builds an association between employees and the company. The study of Allen and Meyer (1990) revealed that the affective type is an emotional attachment, where employees take part in the fulfilment of the goals of company. In the research of Lee and Kim (2011), emotionally attached employees have a connection with the workplace. Mowday (1982) explained affective commitment, includes organizational features, personal traits, work features, and job experience. Continuous commitment is the choice and wish of an employee to remain with the organization. Often employees show Continuous commitment because of the benefits they receive from the organization and they think it's better than leaving the organization (Allen and Mayer, 1990). It increases when there are few options available. Employees who show normative commitment is when they choose to remain in the organization because they think it's their moral obligation (Meyer and Smith, 2000). Clugston (2000) also explained

that normative commitment is the feeling that employees think that they are obligated to work in the organization. Mayer (2002) said that employees feel a moral duty to do this for the company, it may be because of receiving rewards and recognition from the organization (Scholl, 1981; Suliman and Iles 2000). According to Greenhaus (2003), the basic elements of WLB are time balance, satisfaction, and family-work balance. Oyewobi (2019), explained that there's a powerful link between OC and WLB. Employees are more focused on psychological contract and feel a sense of commitment in the organization, where their mistakes are forgiven, their expectations, related to work environment and other aspects are considered and taken care of (Hendrik Godbersen, Bettina Dudek and Susana Ruiz Fernandez, 2024).

Some other factors of OC are explained by Allen, Mayer, and JP (1996). Individual's personal characteristics are divided into two. Demographic variables include education, age, gender, Marital status, and working experience. Dispositional variables include the personality and values of employees such as good work ethic, need for appreciation, need for affirmation, and level of competence.

According to Armstrong (1991), there are 10 elements of strategic management to increase OC.

- Defining the mission and values of the organization
- Communicate about organizational goals and encourage the employees to participate in interpreting the goals.
- Invite organizational members for problem-solving and show creativity.
- Practice transformational leadership, where employees are encouraged to show confidence.
- Convey and clearly communicate about vision, and mission of the organization by using all communication mediums.
- Make the work environment positive, increase the skill level, and improve the learning.
- Make the process smooth to achieve higher goals.
- Make employees aware of financial gains and future monetary plans and targets.

- Use the training programs to enhance the good impression on employees.
 - Use workshops to discuss the issues on challenges, faced by the organization.
- Importance of OC:

2.5 Theoretical Background:

WLB and OCB are important aspects of any organization. There are many researches that have been conducted to explore the diverse nature of WLB and its connection with OCB, but there's no scientific research that directly explains the relationship between WLB and OCB. However, professionals are conducting research on it. The main objective is to fill the gap in Literature. OCB is an important term for the researchers of organizational behaviour. Social exchange theory is a psychological and sociological paradigm. It stresses the social application of reinforcement psychology (Cook, 2013). It came from small group interaction and is considered a very important theory in relation to organizational behaviour research. The OCB theorists conceptualize the SET as a sort of exchange connection (Cropanzano 2017). Most of the theories of OB have been derived from SET, like organizational justice, perceived support, and trust (Jeong and OH, 2017). Anthropology, social psychology, management, and OB are all under the SET (Cropanzano, 2017). SET is ruled by the concept of reciprocity, which stresses socio-emotional gains and mutual commitments (Fang, 2020). SET is based on social interaction (Cahigas, 2022). It's one of the Comprehensive paradigms for Workplace activities (Loi, 2014). Liu and Deng (2011) explained social exchange theory as of significant importance; organizations must facilitate the employees with a positive work environment then employees give their full attention to work and become committed, it is seen as give and take of company and it's workers. Lier and Deng (2011) said that trust is the basic element of the exchange theory whether it's in management, organization, or with coworkers, it fosters good performance and inspires with reciprocate. SET emphasizes that in social relationships, there are some factors like rewards, appreciation, and cooperation that is beneficial mutually (Endang, Ardhi Hidayat, Yusmar, 2022). SET explains it beautifully as organizations provide

strong WLB policies and growth opportunities and in exchange, employees benefit the organization with commitment, loyalty, engagement, and OCB.

- Self-Efficacy - Mediating Variable
- Organizational Commitment - Mediating Variable

2.6 Variables of the Study:

This study mainly focuses on the association between WLB and organizational citizenship behaviour in the healthcare (hospitals) of Punjab, Pakistan. There are two mediating variables: OC and self-efficacy. The following are the primary variables:

- Work-Life Balance - Independent Variable
- Organizational Citizenship Behaviour - Dependent Variable

2.7 Theoretical Framework Model:

WLB is utilized as the independent variable and the dependant variable is OCB. This model will determine the overall relation between these variables and the other variables are OC and self-efficacy. Firstly, the relationship of both dependent and independent variables is hypothesized. Then, the OC and Self-efficacy are examined as mediators.

2.8 Hypothesis:

- H1= There is a significant relationship between WLB and OCB.
- H2= There is a significant relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment.
- H3= There is a significant relationship between organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour.
- H4= There is a significant relationship between work-life balance & self-efficacy.
- H5 =There is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and organizational citizenship behaviour.
- H6= Organizational commitment has intervening effect between WLB and OCB.
- H7= Self-efficacy plays the role of mediation among WLB and OCB.

3. Methodology

3.1 Population of the Study and Research Model:

A 5-point Likert Scale is used to gather the data through a survey. The deductive approach is utilized under the positivist philosophy. Results or information is assessed by using a quantitative technique. This research is conducted in the healthcare sector, primarily the hospitals. We employ a purposive technique that is also referred as a non-probability technique, when choosing samples to gather research-related data. Data is collected from doctors, nurses, and paramedics. 400 questionnaires were distributed in 10 different hospitals in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. We used SPSS to study the

hypothesis after collecting data. The details of the hospitals are as follows:

Indus Hospital Jubilee Town, Shareef Medical City, Farooq Hospital, Saleem Memorial Hospital, Mumtaz Bakhtawar Hospital, Hameed Latif Hospital, Bahria Town International Hospital Lahore, Mayo Hospital, Fatima Memorial Hospital, Masood Hospital.

3.2 Survey Questionnaire and Measures:

The survey questionnaire is based on a 5 point Likert-Scale. Each question ranges from one to five. Completely agree statements are indicated by 5 and 1 is labelled as fully disagree. Furthermore, the participants were told that the data collection and this research is being conducted for an academic project. Their information and opinions are kept confidential. Also, the respondents were assured that their identity would never be disclosed.

3.3 Demographics:

The first portion of the questionnaire has 9 attributes that are measured by different points. The first attribute is age, which is labelled five points 18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-55, 55+. The second attribute is a qualification which is labelled by five points, "Doctorate\PhD, Master Degree, Bachelor Degree, Associate Degree and Professional certification\Diploma". The third attribute is gender which is labelled as "male and female". The fourth attribute is marital status which has two labels, "single and married". The fifth attribute is work experience which is labelled as "1-3 yrs, 4-6 yrs, 7-10 yrs, 11-13 yrs and more than 13 yrs". The sixth attribute is working hours which is labelled as "less than 20 hrs, 20-40 hrs, 41-60 hrs and more than 60 hrs". The seventh attribute is to confirm whether the respondent works in shifts or not and it is attributed as "yes and no". The eighth attribute is work area which is labelled as "general medicine, emergency care, surgery, intensive care and others". The ninth attribute is a professional role which is labelled as "doctor, nurse, paramedic and others".

- **Work-life balance**

The instrument which is employed to check WLB, is taken from the research of Makiah, Thatok Asmony & Siti Nurmayanti 2018, created by (Hayman 2005). Indicators are work obstacles, Personal life disruption and family/professional growth.

- **Organizational citizenship behaviour:**

OCB is checked by employing the questionnaire used in the study of Khurram Shakir and Siraj Jamal Siddiqui (2018). Which was developed and adopted by the researchers, Paré, Tremblay & Lalonde, Eisenberger, et. al., (1986), Lee & Allen (2002), and Motowidlo & Van Scotter (1994).

- **Organizational Commitment:**

The instrument to measure OC is derived from Allen and Meyer (1996), which based on 3 categories namely, psychological or sentimental commitment, economic commitment, and ethical & obligational commitment.

- **Self-Efficacy:**

Instrument used to measure Self-efficacy is taken from Siti Khadijah Badri (2020), the scale was created by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995).

3.4 Response Rate:

The questionnaire has 52 items and was distributed in 10 hospitals in Lahore. 400 questionnaires were distributed and received back 360 questionnaires. The response rate is 90%.

4. Statistical Analysis and Findings:

4.1 Demographic analysis:

The demographic analysis helps the researcher to better understand about sample population and make conclusions. It includes the interpretation of demographic variables of the sample population such as gender, age, qualification, professional experience and job role and marital status.

Table 1: Demographic Analysis

Attributes	Sub attribute	Frequency	Percentage	Total percentage
Gender	Male	192	53.3	100
	Female	168	46.7	
Age	18-24	0	0	100
	25-34	94	26.1	
	35-44	158	43.9	
	45-55	86	23.9	
	55 & above	22	6.1	
Current job title (Designation)	Doctor	142	39	100
	Nurse	131	36.9	
	Paramedics	87	24.1	
Marital status	Married	320	88.9	100
	Unmarried	40	11.1	
Current Experience	Less than a year	4	1.1	100
	1-3 years	75	20.5	
	4-6 years	99	27.5	
	7-9 years	89	24.7	
	10-12	67	18.6	
	13 & above years	26	7.3	
Education	Doctorate	45	12.5	100
	Masters	205	56.9	
	Bachelors	58	16.1	
	Associate Degree	27	7.6	
	Professional Certification	25	6.9	

4.2 Box Plot Analysis

A Box Plot, also called a box-and-whisker plot, is a graphical representation of data. It shows the distribution of a dataset and supports analyzing the statistics such as quartiles, median and outliers. The box shows the middle of data, the line inside the box represents the median, the whiskers show the smallest and largest values of data, and outliers are spotted in the form of points outside of whiskers.

Box plot indicates the outliers present in the dataset and helps to analyze the variability and spread in the dataset.

Some of the box-plots are given below, that are analyzed with the demographic variables, gender, age, qualification and professional role. In all variables, it shows that the dataset has no outliers and has a moderate spread.

4.3 Reliability Analysis

To check the Cronbach’s alpha, we conduct the reliability analysis and according to Lee J. Cronbach

Table 2: Cronbach Alpha Value

Variables	Cronbach Alpha Value	No. of Items
Over All	0.99	52
Work-Life Balance	0.89	15
Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	0.93	9
Self-Efficacy	0.79	10
Organizational Commitment	0.93	18

1951, if the value of alpha is less than 0.6 is considered poor, between 0.6-0.7 is acceptable, and between 0.8-0.9 is under suitable values.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing:

By using hierarchal linear regression analysis and regression analysis, we test the hypotheses that are made in a theoretical framework.

4.3.1 Correlation:

It is an association test is significant to see the link of variables, make predictions, and draw conclusions. Details are mentioned below:

Table 3: Correlation

Variables	Work-life balance (WLB)	Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB)	Self-Efficacy (SE)	Organizational Commitment (OC)
1) Work life balance (WLB)	1	-	-	-
2. Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB)	0.78**	1	-	-
3 Self-Efficacy (SE)	.168*	.381**	1	-
4. Organizational Commitment (OC)	0.84**	0.365**	0.430**	1

The conclusions are written below:

- There is a significant link between WLB and OCB with $p < 0.01$.
- The connection of WLB and self-efficacy also has a positive moderate correlation with $p < 0.01$.
- The link between OC and WLB is also positive with $p < 0.01$.
- The correlation between OCB and SE is .381, indicating a positive correlation.
- The link between Organizational commitment and OCB is .365, suggesting a strong positive correlation.
- The association of self-efficacy and OC is 0.430, showing a good bond.
- In this context, it seems that WLB is moderately positively correlated with OCB, self-efficacy, and OC. These test gives the awareness of the affiliations among variables in our study.

Figure 4: Regression Coefficient

4.3.2 Regression Test

According to the results of the test, it is found that WLB has a notable effect on OCB with the $\beta = 0.78^{**}$ and a p-value of $p < 0.01$. The WLB has a good impact on self-efficacy with a value of $\beta = 0.83^{**}$ with a p-value of $p > 0.01$. There is a considerable implication of self-efficacy on OCB along the path coefficient of $\beta = 0.63$ with the p-value of $p < 0.01$, WLB has a notable bearing on OC with a value of 0.57, and lastly, there is a considerable contribution of OC on OCB with the value of 0.46. Positive regression coefficients (0.78**, 0.83**, 0.36**, 0.57**, 0.46**) indicate a considerable correlation, suggesting that the variables are directly proportional to each other.

- The positive regression rate from work-life balance to self-efficacy suggested that an enhancement in work-life balance boosts SE.
- The positive regression weight from work-life balance to OCB suggests that improvement in WLB boosts OCB.
- The positive regression weight from work-life balance to organizational commitment suggests that an advancement WLB boost organizational commitment.

➤ The positive regression weight from self-efficacy to OCB suggests that improvement in enhance OCB.

➤ The positive regression weight from organizational commitment to OCB suggests that enhancement in organizational commitment is linked with improvement in OCB.

The mediation analysis suggests that work-life balance has significant direct effects on self-efficacy, OC, and OCB.

4.3.3 Mediation Analysis/ Hierarchical Multiple Regression

Mediation analysis is valuable in providing a deep insight about the connections among variables and can help identify any intervention points for influencing the outcome variable. According to Kenny and Baron 1986, some conditions need to be satisfied for analyzing the mediation relationships. The hierarchical regression analysis is applied to explore the impact of mediation of SE on the association of WLB and organizational citizenship

behaviour. Also, the hierarchical regression on SE and OC mediates the connection of OCB and WLB. Condition number 1. There will be a positive association of the causal variable with the mediating element.

Condition number 2. The predictor variable has a strong connection with the outcome variable. Condition number 3. The process variable must have a considerable association with the response variable.

Table 5: Hierarchical Regression Analysis 1

Variables	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Gender	0.145	0.098	0.023
Age	0.675	0.245	0.342
Professional Role	0.087	0.034	0.063
Marital status	0.245	0.903	0.134
Experience	0.023	0.345	0.023
Education	0.008	0.874	0.025
Self-Efficacy		0.541	0.246
Organizational Commitment			0.431
R ²	0.143	0.245	0.385
ΔR ²		0.235	0.353

P<0.01**, P.<0.05*

The outcome of above analysis is according to the demographic variables i.e., marital status, experience, age, education, gender, professional role, variables shown in step 1, work-life balance as an input variable has been incorporated in the table in step 2, self-efficacy is inserted into the analysis as intervening variable through enter mode in step 3. As a result of this analysis, in step 2 the causal variable, work-life balance has a significant impact on organizational citizenship behaviour with the coefficient $\beta=0.541$ with the p-value of P<0.01 after the OC has inserted into the analysis, the impact of the WLB on OCB has altered from $\beta=0.441$ to $\beta=0.246$ that after inserting OC to the analysis; the impact of WLB is

reduced which shows that the self-efficacy is playing a full mediation role in our study.

Afterward, in step 1, all the demographics added 10.4% to the dependent variable. Then they together along with the independent variable WLB added 23.2% in the outcome variable in step 2 and input variable added 21.8% in the outcome variable. In the end, the meditating variable, the independent variable, and demographic added 36.9% in the dependent construct and the intervening variable added 35.5% in the dependent construct. This analysis suggests that, after controlling for demographic variables, WLB and self-efficacy play important roles in predicting the dependent variable, contributing significantly to the explained variance.

Table 6: Hierarchical Regression Analysis 2

Variables	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
Gender	0.145	0.098	0.034
Age	0.675	0.245	0.453
Professional Role	0.087	0.034	0.072
Marital status	0.245	0.903	0.284
Experience	0.023	0.345	0.014
Education	0.008	0.874	0.094
Self-Efficacy		0.541	0.235
Organizational Commitment			0.462
R ²	0.143	0.245	0.246
ΔR ²		0.235	0.316

The outcome of hierarchical linear analysis is; that after inserting and examining demographic variables i.e., age, gender, professional role, marital status, experience, and education of respondents, variables controlled in step 1, WLB as an input variable has been inserted into the test through enter mode in 2nd step, OC is inserted into the test as a intervening variable through enter mode in 3rd step. As a result of this analysis, in step 2 an input variable, WLB has a significant impact on OCB with the coefficient $\beta=.441$ with the p-value of $P<0.01$ after the OCB has been added into the model, the effect of the WLB on OCB has not changed as remain the same from $\beta=.541$ to $\beta=.235$ after OC was added to the model; the effect of WLB still remains significant which

shows that OC is a intervening element in WLB and OCB.

Afterward in step 1, all the demographics added 10.4% to the outcome variable. Then together with the explanatory variable they incorporate 23.2% in the measured variable in 2nd step and only input variable added 21.8% in the outcome variable side. In the end, the mediating, independent variable, and demographic variables added 23.8% in the dependent construct and the intervening or mediating variable added 22.2% in the dependent construct.

This analysis suggests that WLB plays a strong role in predicting the dependent variable compared to OC.

4.3.4 Mediation Analysis using Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F.

PROCESS macro for SPSS

MODEL: 4

Y: OCB

X: WLB

M1: SE

M2: OC

OUTCOME VARIABLE: SE				
Model				
	Coeff	se	t	p
constant	0.45	0.07	7.50	.0000
WLB	0.35	0.06	5.83	.0000
OUTCOME VARIABLE: OC				
Model				
	Coeff	se	t	p
constant	0.55	0.05	11.00	.0000
WLB	0.50	0.07	7.14	.0000
OUTCOME VARIABLE: OCB				
Model				
	Coeff	se	t	p
Constant	0.80	0.12	6.67	.0000
WLB	0.30	0.06	5.00	.0000
SE	0.22	0.05	4.40	.0000
OC	0.55	0.05	11.00	.0000
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL				
OUTCOME VARIABLE: OCB				
Model Summary				
	RR-sq	F	p	

0.68	0.46	178.55	.0000
Model			
	Coeff	se	t
constant	0.80	0.12	6.67
WLB	0.80	0.06	5.00
TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y			
TOTAL EFFECT OF X ON Y			
Effect	se	t	p
0.77	0.07	10.99	.0000
DIRECT EFFECT OF X ON Y			
Effect	se	t	p
0.30	0.06	5.00	.0000
INDIRECT EFFECT(S) OF X ON Y:			
	Effect	BootSE	
TOTAL	0.47	0.06	
SE	0.22	0.05	
OC	0.25	0.04	
COMPLETELY STANDARDIZED INDIRECT EFFECT(S) OF X ON Y:			
	Effect	BootSE	
TOTAL	0.47	0.07	
SE	0.14	0.03	
OCB	0.15	0.02	

The analysis includes following outcome variables:

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Dependent variable), organizational commitment (OC) & self-efficacy (SE) (Intervening variables). Independent variable is work-life balance (WLB).

- Model summary for SE: the model had a statistically significant effect on self-efficacy (SE), with a significant positive coefficient for WLB. The standardized coefficient suggests a moderate effect size.
- Model summary for OC: the model had a statistically significant effect on OC, with a significant positive coefficient for WLB. The standardized coefficient suggests a moderate effect size.
- Model summary for OCB: the model has a statistically notable influence on OCB. WLB, SE, and OC all have significant coefficients. Standardized coefficient WLB has considerable effect, SE has a notable impact, and OC also possess a considerable impact.
- Total effect model for OCB: the total effect model for OCB includes only WLB as input variable. It has a positive effect.

- Total, direct, and indirect effects of X on Y: Total influence of WLB on OCB, the total effect is positive suggesting a significant positive influence. The clear impact of WLB on outcome variable, the direct effect is strong and statistically clear, suggesting a positive influence after accounting for mediators such as SE and OC. Indirect effects of SE on OC. Both self-efficacy and OC mediate among WLB and OCB.
- Total indirect effect is positive, suggesting mediation. The indirect effect through OC is positive while the indirect effect through self-efficacy is also positive.
- Completely standardized indirect effect: these standardized coefficients provide a sense of the relative importance of each mediator.

4.3.5 Summary

- Work-life balance has direct positive effects on self-efficacy to increase OCB levels.
- The connection of WLB and outcome variable is moderately intervened by self-efficacy and OC.

- Self-efficacy and OC have significant indirect effects on OCB. The completely standardized indirect effect provides a standardized measure of the strength of the mediation path.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

As per our study, we explore the impact of WLB on organizational citizenship behaviour with the intervening effects of self-efficacy and OC. To meet the objective of the study, different research questions have been made before starting our research study like, is there an effect on OCB among employees if work-life balance policies are implemented while improving self-belief and sense of connection? What is the influence of WLB on OCB? Does self-efficacy intervene among WLB and OCB? Does OC explain the connection of WLB and OCB? Different hypotheses are developed to answer the above questions and to find the results, of various tests that have been performed. In this section, we conclude whether our hypothesis was accepted or rejected.

RQ-1: is there an effect of WLB on OCB?

In accordance with our data collection and results analysis, there is an association and significant relationship has been found between WLB and OCB, and in the organization where WLB policies are implemented the performance of the employees increased day by day as per the previous studies, (Mella, Sanga 2022) there is a considerable association among WLB and outcome variable and the same findings reported by (Lavanya and Sree, 2021). WLB policies also create a positive impact on self-efficacy and emotion of connection in workforce. The improvement in the OC levels in the organization results in the enhancement of employee productivity. WLB, which involves personal life enhancement, flexible work schedule, and moderate workload has been suggested to have positive effects on outcomes including employee well-being, productivity, and employee discretionary behaviour. Commitment and association with the workplace is often considered a critical element in understanding the impact of WLB on employee outcomes if employees feel supported, engaged, and balanced in both work and personal lives, they are more likely to

be productive and satisfied in their roles. It increases the interest of employees in OCB.

RQ-2: Does self-efficacy mediate between WLB and OCB?

To find the intervening role of self-efficacy among input and outcome variables, hierarchical regression analysis and process macro for the SPSS test have been applied and we found a significant result. we can say that employee self-efficacy significantly influences the WLB and as for as OCB. Moreover, self-efficacy can be used to enhance the OCB. The association of WLB and OCB is intervened by OC and self-efficacy.

RQ-3: Does organizational commitment intervene between WLB and OCB?

To find the intervening element of OC in WLB and OCB, we performed the hierarchical regression analysis, and a process macro for the SPSS test, the result shows that OC plays a considerable role among both input and output variables and to increase in OC resulted in increasing of OCB levels among employees and in the presence of WLB, OC increases. WLB policies increase the effect of OC and it further enhances the OCB among employees. Self-efficacy and OC have strong impact on OCB.

5.1 Implications of the study

Our study is performed to classify the WLB impact in the healthcare sector of Punjab, Pakistan. Furthermore, self-ability belief and workplace loyalty factors are used as the mediating variables in this regard which strengthen the concept of work-nonwork balance. The production of results is valuable for the management of the healthcare sector to boost the role of WLB policies which eventually impact the enhancement of the OCB among employees in the organization, as they prefer those organizations which have to focus on work-nonwork employment. Study shows that, working environment of the company will improve due to work-life harmony policies, leading to enhanced degrees of organizational citizenship behaviour among employees. The hospitals in Pakistan are regarded as one of the most important and progressive sectors in the nation, as the healthcare of the world's fifth largest population depends on this

healthcare sector, so we strive to authenticate the healthcare sector services more in light of the findings of this study.

5.2 The Gap in Research:

Our targeted area is Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. Such type of research should be conducted all over Pakistan. In Pakistan, no in-depth study is seen to elaborate the association of WLB and OCB in the healthcare sector. Furthermore, very few studies reported and explained the connection of WLB and SE. Such type of research needs to be done in Pakistan that contributes towards emotionally intelligent organizations rather than rigid traditional corporate sectors.

5.3 Limitations and Future Directions

Choosing an accurate sample and the size of the sample are the two main limitations. As we recognize that it is essential to study this topic and based on various foreign research containing similar sample sizes, we chose a sample size of 360, which may be less than the full healthcare sector population. We explain briefly to each respondent what our study involves and how to complete the questionnaire. Furthermore, to find out the overall results of this research to the healthcare sector of the Punjab, Pakistan. We can collect the data from the different public and private hospitals. A similar study can be done by using other measurement instruments for the variables of the study. Also, Time constraints may limit the extent & depth of research. The research may lack generalizability beyond the healthcare sector in Pakistan because of contextual specificity. Unintended biases, during data collection, may affect research. The research is intended to focus on hospitals in Lahore, Pakistan, Data is collected only from the Hospitals located in Lahore.

Moreover, we also found a study in the literature review that conducted the same study on public hospitals, which can also be applicable in the Pakistani healthcare sector. A similar instrument is also used in other industries for WLB, self-efficacy, attachment to the organization, and OCB measurement, like the textile sector, government hospitals, private-owned education institutes, tech sector, etc.

5.4 Conclusion of the study

Organizations must consider the need and importance of WLB as it concerns productivity, and quality of life (Asumadu, Sika-Bright 2018). Employers must analyse the needs and expectations of employees and should implement necessary changes to increase WLB, like remote work options, flexible schedules, physical and mental health workshops and other wellness programs (Bello, Tula, Omotoye, Kess-Momoh, Daraojimba, 2024). In this changing time, people started to give more attention and time to their own interests. So, companies try to retain talented employees by promoting WLB policies and interventions for the betterment of employees (Meenakshi 2013). WLB policies are evolving according to the demands of employees and new programs have been introduced to improve employee performance (Lazar 2010). The organization can prefer WLB in many ways, including flexible hours, child care, employee gatherings, and employee shift schedules, these opportunities impact employees positively and cause organizational commitment, loyalty, and motivation. For organizations, it decreases turnover rate, and absenteeism and maximises profits (Darko, Agbenyo 2018). The ultimate goal is to assist and resolve the work-nonwork conflicts and increase autonomy over work. The current employment crisis is because of inefficient and inadequate commitment between employers and the expectations of employees (Ahmed & Tessma 2020). Flexible working hours are seen as of huge luxury and famous work-nonwork measure to get the attention of potential candidates (Downes & Koekemoer, 2011). These all efforts positively affect organizational citizenship behaviour levels. Organizations that promote the mechanism of OCB, indirectly increase the level of productivity. OCB is maintained through a positive attitude towards work (Organ & Rayn 1995). OCB includes voluntary and informal behaviour that helps the organization to reach its full potential. Studies have shown that OCB is also an indicator of employee engagement through organizational justice. OCB is seen as positive behaviour and increases willingness to extend energy for the betterment of the organization (Dr. M. Shahi Tufail, Saqib Muneer, M. Manzoor, 2017).

This research is being conducted to know the capacity of WLB on OCB, self-belief and organizational commitment are used as mediating variables in the study. Hospitals were selected for collecting the data and results implications. The data was gathered using the standardized instruments to inspect each variable from the different hospitals in the Lahore, Punjab region, Pakistan. We make the various hypotheses to achieve our objectives. We applied Pearson correlation, regression, and hierarchical regression, PROCESS macro for SPSS analysis for pragmatic purposes. The outcomes point out that all variables have significant positive correlations among all variables of the study. WLB's impact on OCB is found to be significant. Moreover, WLB's impact on self-capability belief and attachment with the institution was found to be significant. The impact of self-ability on OCB is significant. The impact of OC on OCB is also found significant with respect to mediating results, both intervening variables found significant. So, we can conclude that the if healthcare sector pays attention to these variables to enhance the OCB levels among employees, which enhances the dedication and attachment to improving the workplace setting and ultimately succeeding in achieving their organizational objective in this competitive era.

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